

A Randomized Approach to Securing 5G Networks Against Rogues

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Abstract

In this paper, we consider endogenous attacks on 5G networks. These attacks are potentially more deleterious than exogenous attacks since rogues possess privileged knowledge of the network's structure and operation which makes benign nodes vulnerable. We propose a network reconfiguration strategy to mitigate the possibility of such attacks. In the sequel we will perform a mathematical analysis of the attack and defense based on [1].

1 Introduction

Since their inception, 5G networks have been the state-of-the-art in networking technology for many application domains. Their rich capabilities [2, 3] mean that they are widely deployed. One of the key areas of research is therefore security and privacy in these networks. Some of the advantages of 5G networks over 3G and 4G networks include: high speed, low latency, high capacity and network slicing [4, 5]. At the physical layer, 5G networks use technologies that enable broader coverage areas, as well as better error correction techniques that enable reliable transmission [6, 7].

The rich repertoire of possible uses of 5G networks makes them vulnerable targets of malicious attacks. There are several possible attacks against a cellular network: the ToRPEDO, the PIERCER and various Denial-of-Service attacks [8, 9, 10]. Inspired by the antibody-antigen system present in biological organisms, herein we divide attacks into two categories - exogenous and endogenous, and focus on the latter in Section 3.5. We present a review of literature in Section 2. In Section 3 we present the problem background. In Section 4 we present a possible strategy to mitigate endogenous attacks, including the use of perceptrons which we analyze in some detail. In Section 6 we conclude with a discussion of limitations and future work.

2 Literature Review

The aim of this section is to present a review of a couple of relevant papers that discuss the attacks we are interested in. We first discuss [8]. In this paper, the

authors study 5G and 4G networks, with the goal of identifying vulnerabilities to various types of attacks. In particular, they propose a Torpedo attack and its countermeasure. In this attack, the attacker is able to accurately locate the victim in a geographical cell and thereafter launch a couple of more attacks which completely recover the victim’s identity. Then they propose the Piercer attack which similarly allows location tracking of the victim. Another attack discussed is the IMSI-Cracking attack for 4G/5G networks.

In [11], the authors review the Denial of Service attack and the Torpedo attacks. They also discuss countermeasures to these attacks. [12] is an early survey of security in information operations. Along with defining what defensive information operations do, it also mentions the role of artificial neural networks in acquiring data from the network for analysis and prediction in the security context.

In Lee-Yang-Han [13], a network of “point cloud” for semantic image segmentation is formed. Since fully supervised learning in this context is time consuming, the authors propose weakly supervised segmentation. They quantified uncertainty in a segmentation via entropy and reduced it by computing the graphical information gain via what they call “reliable information.” They performed extensive simulations and showed the superiority or effectiveness of their method over competing ones. The network here may be represented as a graph with labels or partial labels. There are no security issues or privacy issues of concern. Learning is performed on the network and it tends towards unsupervised learning. In contrast, the present paper utilizes a graphical representation for 5G communication networks and network security is the key issue. Supervised learning is performed on the network nodes, also in contrast to Lee-Yang-Han.

In Shutta et. al. [14], gaussian graphical networks are used to model multi-layered “omics” datasets, and capture the inter-relationships between and within layers. The DRAGON package, as applied to these networks, is shown to perform well in determining underlying models and recovering model edges. This semi-analytical study also uses simulations to adjudicate performance of the DRAGON framework. Again, there are no security issues, this is not a communication network at heart, and they don’t do machine learning but rather perform parameter estimation.

In Cao et. al. [15], the authors deal with the problem of voltage distribution. They utilize a layered structure for their algorithms. The layers include a deep reinforcement learning (DRL) method, a global graph attention network (GGAT) and a deep auto-encoder (DAE). The latter two deal with structural information and informative features making the solution robust to measurement errors. The DRL algorithm gets its reward signal from a graphical-learning-based model. Explicit algorithms are presented for the training of the voltage control method and the representation network. The overall performance is compared with a handful of other methods. Thus in this paper, we have a representation network related to voltage distribution, which can be thought of as a commodity flow network - slightly distinct from a communication network. Graphical learning and other machine learning techniques are utilized for solv-

Figure 1: Three bimodal graphical networks. Sub-figures b and c are reflections of one another. Each has two hub nodes and three satellite nodes. Sub-figure a has six nodes altogether, three of each type.

ing the problem, and in this the paper is similar to the present paper where machine learning is used as an aspect of the solution to the problem of security of a graphical communication network.

3 Problem Background

3.1 Bimodal Graphs and Networks

For motivation, consider a grove in which there are five trees with three beehives each. Bees regularly go from one beehive to the other, whether on the same tree or another tree. But occasionally, the queen bee visits a neighboring queen bee. This is a different type of visit altogether. Thus the network of bees comes to have two types of loci - the regular nodes which are the bees and the special nodes which are the queens. This is known as a bimodal network¹.

Definition 1. A bimodal graph is one where there can be two different types of nodes. For example, UE (user-equipment) and R (router).

Notation: One can represent a bimodal graph by specifying N_1 and N_2 as the number of nodes of each type, E , the number of edges between nodes and Ψ , the assignment function which assigns a pair of nodes to each edge. Thus the model becomes (N_1, N_2, E, ψ) . Figure 1 illustrates such a graph.

Definition 2. A bimodal network is a network whose graph is bimodal.

¹In similar networks of fireflies, Mirollo and Strogatz have characterized their synchronization [16, 17].

3.2 Rogues

A party of three monks is traveling down a dusty path in mid-summer northern India. A carriage of two riders comes abreast of the party. One of the monks begins trading with the two riders, bartering goods. The carriage moves on. After half a day, the monk with the bartered goods thinks to himself that his new goods are useful beyond his preconception and that he could entice the other monks to barter with him.

This fictional occurrence, set in mid 100 BCE, shows the basic mechanism of turning rogue or departing from one's principled membership in a group. Thus, a rogue node is defined as a previously normal node of the network, that 'turns' into an adversary for any reason. In what follows we will assume a bimodal graphical network (N_1, N_2, E, ψ) , but we will make the further assumption that nodes in the set N_1 do not start any type of attack. Thus all potential rogue nodes belong to the set N_2 .

3.3 The Immunological Model

The human immune system is known to defend the body against pathogens. The immune cells gather around and annihilate the intruders. Sometimes, in autoimmune diseases, the immune cell attacks its own system. Whereas there have been studies involving the immune system in more detail and using it to design wireless sensor networks and intrusion detection systems [18], in the present work we will only take broad inspiration from the immune system. The auto-antigen will be called a rogue in our 5G context. This is a bona-fide node in the network.

3.4 Cases of Interest

Networks can be grouped by the number of rogues present in them at any time. Based on this, we can identify a few cases of interest for modeling purposes:

1. One rogue in the network ($n = 1$)
2. Two rogues in the network ($n = 2$)
3. General case: n rogues in the network with N_2 modality-2 nodes.

3.5 The Endogenous Attack and its Detection: Overview

In a normal large network, not every node will be present in the repertoire of a given node. We are interested in endogenous attacks against distant nodes, not present in the working repertoire of the given node. Since the auto-antigen node is part of the network, it can correctly correlate a placed call with the resulting paging message, in order to unleash further disruption.

The detection of the endogenous attack is straightforward, since after the node goes rogue and obtains the location of the victim, it can launch one of the known, standard attacks of the three types considered in this paper. The

Figure 2: Exogenous and Endogenous Attacks.

regular detection strategy for the detection of those attacks (for the exogenous case) can be applied to the endogenous case with slight modification.

3.6 Specifics of Disruption Caused

A rogue can compromise network security and privacy in several possible ways. For example, by flooding a particular node’s incoming stream, the rogue can induce denial-of-service. The rogue can also perform Torpedos and, possibly, Piercers [8]. In a Torpedo the attacker can learn the victim’s geographical location in a cell with less than ten calls and can cause further damage as well. In a Piercer attack the attacker, with a fake base station, can associate the victim’s phone number with its subscriber identity. However, since a fake base station is required in a Piercer attack, it may not be feasible for a rogue to fully implement it.

3.7 Detection of Disruption

The disruption caused can be detected by its “effects.” This is a high-latency mechanism of detection and a more effective detection mechanism would be needed. Some of the ideas of an “adaptive” immune system in [19] can be utilized. An adaptive immune system is present in the human body over and beyond the innate immune system. By aggregating danger signals from the innate immune system, it acts as a second layer of defense.

4 A Solution: Network Random Refresh (NRR)

In this section we describe how an endogenous attack of a specific type, the theme of this paper, can be prevented. We introduce a novel approach called

Network Random Refresh to secure 5G networks.

4.1 Random Configuration

Suppose the network configuration, that is, a graphical representation of the network, including the list of inter-nodal distances is randomly and periodically reconfigured. By this we mean the following. Suppose there is a ‘file’ which contains details of how the network is systematically arranged, information about which node is connected to which other node, and what are the protocols in place for communication between those nodes. We’ll call this the configuration file. It applies to the entire network, to the remotest node. By a re-configuration, we mean that we will take this file and modify some of the details. For example, we may alter the fact that node 2 is connected to (can talk to) node 20 easily via protocol B and insert instead the commandment that node 2 cannot talk to node 20 at all, it can only communicate with any node within 3 hops of it, and that too only via protocol A. Once we are finished with making all these and sundry changes, we say the new file specifies a network re-configuration.

4.2 Random Timing

Further, by allowing the timing of when the re-configuration is made, to be ‘random’, we mean that there isn’t a fixed formula for determining if the network needs to be presently re-configured. Instead, a coin is tossed at each discrete time step, so to say, and if it lands on Heads, one reconfigures the network using the new file, and if on Tails, one leaves the present configuration in place.

4.3 Implications for Rogues

This random, periodic re-configuration implies that no single node could ever be sure of correlating a call it places with the resulting paging message. In turn, this guarantees that a node gone rogue can be contained. This can be easily seen as follows. Suppose I’m a rogue node and I wish to attack the network. For this I need to know the configuration file. I have one on hand. I start to use it to determine which node to attack and how to reach it, using which protocol. As I begin to implement my strategy, the coin is tossed and the network is refreshed, voila, a new configuration file is in place. So my efforts have been in vain.

4.4 Addressing the non-Rogue Setting

On the flip-side, when such rare rogue events are not occurring, the rule for obtaining the list of inter-nodal distances (essential for successfully matching a call with the resulting paging message) should be modified in such a way that two nodes would share the table of inter-nodal distances between them, each normally possessing only half of it. When a node needs to make a call, it would be required to first establish nearest-neighbor communication and obtain the other half of the table from the neighbor. This implies that two nodes would be

required to go rogue together, at minimum in order for an endogenous attack to be executed.

4.5 Summary of the NRR Mitigation/Counter-measure

We proposed “Network Random Refresh” (NRR) as a counter-measure to a probable rogue attack. In NRR an unbiased coin is tossed at every discrete time instant and if the coin lands on ‘Heads,’ then the network is refreshed into a new random state. By a random state we mean that whereas (N_1, N_2, E) remain unchanged, a random assignment function ψ_r is used. Furthermore, in a future work, we can also allow random re-allocation of communication protocols along various edges. The NRR is performed subject to constraints. These constraints specify that more ‘changes’ need to be put in place in areas where there are suspected rogues than in areas where there are mostly trusted nodes.

4.6 Ensuring good service on non-rogue-event days

On most days, there won’t be rogue activity in the network. If NRR is in place, how do we ensure that the network doesn’t get too bogged down in all these refreshes and remains functional? Assume that after each refresh the network tells each node the new ψ_r function, however concealing part of it. The information is provided in such a way that by one “conversation” with a nearest neighbor, a node can acquire the complete picture of the ψ_r function; this allows good activity to go on. At the same time, it deters ‘lone-wolf’ rogues who would be reluctant to establish a conversation with anyone as it might reveal their malicious intent.

As a note, overall connectivity is maintained while choosing a new ψ_r , even though specific edges may no longer exist or be added; only this can guarantee that the network is still useful and functional.

4.7 Allocation and Detection of Rogues

One can ‘throw’ rogues randomly onto the network’s nodes, thereby converting them into rogues. It may be possible to analytically show in this setting, that the probability is low for two nearest neighbor nodes to both be allocated as rogues, thereby avoiding the case where two rogues together get access to the entire ψ_r .

As mentioned, a rogue is detected by its deleterious “effects.” The question arises as to who observes and decides that such and such an effect is deleterious. There are at least two possibilities:

- a. Local Observer: Under this setting, there is a central observer which decides whether nodes are behaving odd or not.
- b. Global/non-local/Distributed observer: Under this setting, a distributed ML algorithm acting over time detects and predicts the presence of nodes.

Figure 3: Perceptron schematic.

4.8 Rogue Detection Using Coupled Ephaptic Perceptrons

Whereas a number of machine learning approaches might be useful in detecting rogues, we limit ourselves to a type of perceptron algorithm. Towards this end, we propose a type of perceptron with branching and coupling. The proposed perceptron is distinct from known neural network structures, including convolutional neural networks. The paper [20] mentions how one can choose the size of the fan-in and number of weights of a perceptron.

In the following subsections we do a rigorous analysis of the perceptron’s performance using simulations. This is done as a stepping stone towards analyzing and characterizing the performance of the ephaptic branched perceptron. This latter algorithm has made its appearance in recent literature [21] though not in the exact form considered here.

4.9 Introduction to the Ephaptic Perceptron

Rosenblatt [22] introduced the regular perceptron. Feedforward versions are investigated by Fine in [23]. There are numerous applications and fundamental studies related to it [24, 25, 26]. In 2023, Zeleny et. al. [21] introduced a branched multi-layer perceptron which is perhaps inspired by branching seen in real neurons. It differs from the regular multi-layer perceptron in that it has multiplication and addition layers on top of the fully-connected layer that is used in the multi-layer perceptron. Other variations of the perceptron have also been reported in the literature [27].

The perceptron is one of the early algorithms that can be called a learning algorithm. Learning has long been associated with intelligence. Being a mathematical model, one can ask if the model represents a real biological object or not. Whereas perceptrons are inspired by neurons, they also differ in many ways. We wonder if a more accurate perceptron model can not be built and if that would not enhance performance or imitation of natural intelligence. Whereas we don’t address this issue directly, we do comment on it in passing towards the end of this document.

In this and the following subsections we do a rigorous study of the regular

perceptron for a simple case and perform Python simulations to validate it. Additionally, we propose new variations on the perceptron which can be analyzed in a similar way in future work. This and the following subsections are organized as follows. We briefly review the regular perceptron in Subsection 4.11.1 of Section 4.11. In Subsection 4.11.2 we perform the statistical analysis of the regular perceptron. In Subsection 4.11.3 we study the training phase in detail. In Subsection 4.12 we introduce a few novel perceptron types.

4.10 The Ephaptic Perceptron Vs. the Multi-layer Perceptron

In this subsection we compare these two perceptrons mathematically.

4.11 Statistical Analysis

4.11.1 The Regular Perceptron

In this section we present a quick summary of the central fact related to the perceptron. The perceptron is governed by a key weight update equation:

$$w[2] = w[1] + \eta * (d[1] - y[1]) * x[1] \quad (1)$$

where w stands for weights, η is the learning rate parameter, d is the desired classification based on training labels, y is the actual classification and x is the input data. Figure 3 presents a schematic of the perceptron.

4.11.2 Statistical Study

In the following, we assume a probability density function (p.d.f.) for the dataset. However, most often this is unknown and we must try a number of different p.d.f.'s. In this context, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) can be of help [28]. Nevertheless, in the present section we assume Gaussianity.

Assume that $x_1(n)$, where n is the discrete time index has the probability density function $f_{x_1}^1(x_1)$. Likewise, we have $f_{x_2}^1(x_2)$, $f_{x_3}^1(x_3)$ and so on, up to $f_{x_m}^1(x_m)$. As an example consider 60000 black-and-white images provided with handwritten characters on them. For each pixel we can find its empirical probability mass function (p.m.f.). Then, when we take the first image, its second pixel will be a "random" sample drawn from $f_{x_2}(x_2)$. Effectively, $f_{x_2}^1(x_2) = f_{x_2}^2(x_2) = f_{x_2}^3(x_2) = \dots = f_{x_2}(x_2)$.

But, actually, there's a larger, joint probability mass function $f_{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_M}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_M)$. Treating x_1, \dots, x_M as a vector \vec{x} , $f_{\vec{x}}(\vec{x}) \equiv f_{x_1, \dots, x_M}(x_1, \dots, x_M)$. This is the input probability mass function (p.m.f.). Suppose, $f_{\vec{x}}(\vec{x}) = f(x_1, \dots, x_M; \mu, \sigma)$ where μ is the M-by-1 mean vector and Σ is the M-by-M covariance matrix. Then [29],

$$f_{\vec{x}}(\vec{x}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2 * \pi)^M * det(\Sigma)}} * e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\vec{x}-\vec{\mu}) * \Sigma^{-1} * (\vec{x}-\mu)}. \quad (2)$$

Next, let each $w_{i=1}^M$ be drawn initially i.i.d. from $U[0, 1]$ which is the uniform p.d.f. on $[0, 1]$. Then, if

$$J_i \equiv X_i \cdot W_i \quad (3)$$

where i goes from 1 through M , using the fact the joint p.d.f. of two independent random variables is the product of the marginal p.d.fs, we get,

$$f_{J_1}(j_1) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{|x_1|} * f_{x_1}(x_1) * f_{w_1}(j_1/x_1) dx_1. \quad (4)$$

Further, we can express the weights' p.d.f. as $f_{W_1}(w_1) = 0$, if $w_1 \leq 0$ or $w_1 \geq 1$ and 1 otherwise. This enables us to write $f_{W_1}(j_1/x_1) = 0$, if $x_1 \leq j_1$ or $j_1 \leq 0$ and 1 otherwise. Thus, upon simplifying Equation (4), we get

$$f_{J_1}(j_1) = \int_{j_1}^{\infty} \frac{f_{X_1}(x_1)}{|x_1|} dx_1 \quad (5)$$

for $j_1 \geq 0$ and 0 otherwise. If we define J as the post-summation stage of the perceptron, we get,

$$J = J_1 + J_2 + \dots + J_M \quad (6)$$

where M is the number of weights in the perceptron.

Following Shannon's strategy of simplifying a problem to the barest case, solving it first, and then adding complexity, we consider first the case of $M = 2$. This case might even suffice for us since we are only interested in the 'comparative' performance, not absolute performance of these various neural networks. Using Equation (3) and assuming (a very strong initial assumption) that X_1 and X_2 are independent of each other, we get that J_1 and J_2 are also independent of one another since the W_i are i.i.d, with no dependence on the X_i . Thus the pdf of the sum $J_1 + J_2$ is the convolution of the marginal pdfs. Since X_1 and X_2 are independent, assuming that they are each $N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$, we get that their covariance must be 0. From Equation (5) we have,

$$f_{J_1}(j_1) = 0 \quad (7)$$

if $j_1 < 0$ and

$$f_{J_1}(j_1) = \int_{j_1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 * \pi * \sigma_1^2}} \frac{e^{-\frac{(x_1 - \mu_1)^2}{2 * \sigma_1^2}}}{|x_1|} dx_1 \quad (8)$$

otherwise. Similarly,

$$f_{J_2}(j_2) = 0 \quad (9)$$

if $j_2 < 0$ and

$$f_{J_2}(j_2) = \int_{j_2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 * \pi * \sigma_2^2}} \frac{e^{-\frac{(x_2 - \mu_2)^2}{2 * \sigma_2^2}}}{|x_2|} dx_2 \quad (10)$$

otherwise. This yields, for J ,

$$f_J(z) = \int_0^z \int_{j_1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 * \pi * \sigma_1^2}} \frac{e^{-\frac{(x_1 - \mu_1)^2}{2 * \sigma_1^2}}}{|x_1|} dx_1 \quad (11)$$

$$= \dots \cdot \int_{z - j_1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2 * \pi * \sigma_2^2}} \frac{e^{-\frac{(x_2 - \mu_2)^2}{2 * \sigma_2^2}}}{|x_2|} dx_2 dj_1. \quad (12)$$

This is the p.d.f. of J which is then put through the hard-limiter to yield (following Equation (10-69) of [29]),

$$Pr \{Y = 1\} = 1 - F_J(0), \quad (13)$$

and

$$Pr \{Y = 0\} = F_J(0). \quad (14)$$

where

$$F_J(0) = Pr \{J \leq 0\}. \quad (15)$$

But from Equation (12),

$$F_J(0) = Pr \{J < 0\} = Pr \{J_1 + J_2 < 0\} = \int_{-\infty}^0 f_J(z) dz. \quad (16)$$

Note that $0 < j_1 < z$. But $f_J(z) = 0$ for $z < 0$. Therefore, $F_J(0) = 0$ and so Y is always 1. Suppose consequently we relax the independence assumption, and let,

$$f_{X_1, X_2}(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2 * \pi)^2 * det(\Sigma_2)}} * e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\vec{x} - \vec{\mu})^\dagger \Sigma_2^{-1}(\vec{x} - \vec{\mu})} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\vec{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 \\ \mu_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

and

$$\Sigma_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1^2 & COV(X_1, X_2) \\ COV(X_1, X_2) & \sigma_2^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

Thus,

$$det(\Sigma_2) = [\sigma_1^2 \sigma_2^2 - COV(X_1, X_2)^2] \quad (20)$$

and therefore

$$\Sigma_2^{-1} = \frac{1}{\det(\Sigma_2)} * \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_2^2 & -COV(X_1, X_2) \\ -COV(X_1, X_2) & \sigma_1^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

Therefore,

$$f_{\vec{X}}(\vec{x}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2 * \pi)^2 * (\sigma_1^2 * \sigma_2^2 - C^2)}}. \quad (22)$$

$$.e^{-\frac{[\sigma_1^2(x_2 - \mu_2)^2 + \sigma_2^2(x_1 - \mu_1)^2 + C * [(x_1 - \mu_1)^2 - (x_1 * x_2 + \mu_1 * \mu_2 - \mu_1 * x_2 - \mu_2 * x_1)]]}{2(\sigma_1^2 * \sigma_2^2 - C^2)}}. \quad (23)$$

where C has been used in place of $COV(X_1, X_2)$. Note that $J = J_1 + J_2 = X_1 * W_1 + X_2 * W_2$. We are next interested in the joint distribution of the input and the weights, noting that at initialization and (assuming) at every later stage too, they are independent of each other. We obtain,

$$f_{\vec{X}, \vec{W}}(\vec{x}, \vec{w}) = f_{\vec{X}}(\vec{x}) \quad (24)$$

if $0 < w_1 < 1$ or $0 < w_2 < 1$ and 0 otherwise. Therefore,

$$F_J(j) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{j-x_1} f_{\vec{X}}(\vec{x}) dx_2 dx_1 \quad (25)$$

This last integral has no analytical solution. The error function appears in the solution and so we use a short Python script (Algorithm 1) to evaluate the integral for various values of the input argument. Equation (13) indicates that once $F_J(j)$ is found numerically, that gives us the output distribution.

4.11.3 Training Phase

With $F_J(j)$ in hand we have the hard-limiter output probabilities. Next we need labeled data. We know the joint pdf of (X_1, X_2) . From this, we sample k times. Then we specify a decision boundary $y = m * x + c$. Points falling above the line are assigned the class C1 and those below the line are assigned the class C0. This is accomplished using the Python script in Algorithm 2. The output is shown in Figure 5.

Algorithm 1 Python script used for computing part of the integral in Equation (25).

```

import sympy as sp
import numpy as np
import scipy as scip
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy import integrate
mynumpoints = 10
covset = np.linspace(0.095,0.1,mynumpoints)
arr = [0 for element in range(mynumpoints)]
count = 0
for cov in covset:
    variance1 = 0.7
    variance2 = 0.2
    cov = -1*cov
    mean1 = 5.6
    mean2 = 1.1
    x1 = sp.Symbol('x1')
    x2 = sp.Symbol('x2')
    b_val = variance1 / 2.0 * (variance1 * variance2 - cov**2.0)
    c_val = (cov * mean1 - cov * x1 - 2.0 * variance1 * mean2)/...
... (2.0 * (variance1 * variance2 - cov**2.0))
    g_val = cov * x1
    alpha = (sp.exp(cov*mean1*mean2/(2*(variance1*variance2-cov**2))))/...
... (2*np.pi*np.sqrt(variance1*variance2-cov**2))
    beta = sp.exp(-(variance1*mean2**2)/(2*(variance1*variance2-cov**2)))
    d = (variance2+cov)/(variance1*variance2-cov**2)
    h = -2*mean1*d+(cov*mean2)/(variance1*variance2-cov**2)
    l = mean1**2*d
    inner = sp.exp(-(variance1 / 2.0 * (variance1 * variance2 - cov**2.0))*x
... - (((cov * mean1 - cov * x1 - 2.0 * variance1 * mean2)/...
... (2.0 * (variance1 * variance2 - cov**2.0))) + (cov*x1))*x2)
    myfun = sp.exp(-0.5*((d*x1**2)+h*x1+l))*(sp.exp(-(variance1 / 2.0 * ...
... (variance1 * variance2 - cov**2.0))*x2**2 - ...
... (((cov * mean1 - cov * x1 - 2.0 * variance1 * mean2)/...
... (2.0 * (variance1 * variance2 - cov**2.0))) + (cov*x1))*x2))*alpha*beta
    myfunfun= lambda x1,x2: sp.exp(-0.5*((d*x1**2)+h*x1+l))*...
... (sp.exp(-(variance1 / 2.0 * (variance1 * variance2 - cov**2.0))*x2**2...
... - (((cov * mean1 - cov * x1 - 2.0 * variance1 * mean2)/...
... (2.0 * (variance1 * variance2 - cov**2.0))) + (cov*x1))*x2))*alpha*beta
    newestresult=integrate.dblquad(myfunfun,-np.inf, np.inf, -np.inf, lambda
arr[count]=newestresult[0]
    print(count)
    count = count + 1
x = np.arange(0,mynumpoints)
y = arr
# plotting
plt.title("Class-0 Classification Probability vs Input Covariance")
plt.xlabel("Input Cov(X1,X2)")
plt.ylabel("Probability of Output Y=0")
plt.plot(-covset, y, color="red")
plt.show()

```

Algorithm 2 Python script for creating labeled data.

```
import numpy as np
def joint_pdf(x1, x2):
# Define the joint PDF function here
# Modify this function to match the specific joint PDF you have
# Example joint PDF: a bivariate Gaussian distribution
mean = [1.0, 2.0]
cov = [[1.0, 0.5], [0.5, 2.0]]
return np.random.multivariate_normal(mean, cov)
n = 1000 # Number of samples to generate
m = .10;
intercept = 1.02;
# Generate samples
samples = []
labels = []
for _ in range(n):
x1_sample, x2_sample = joint_pdf(0, 0)
# Pass initial values for x1 and x2
samples.append((x1_sample, x2_sample))
# Print the generated samples
for i, (x1_sample, x2_sample) in enumerate(samples):
print(f"Sample {i+1}: x1 = {x1_sample}, x2 = {x2_sample}")
if x2_sample > m*x1_sample+intercept:
labels.append(1)
print("C1");
else:
labels.append(0)
print("C0")
```

Figure 4: Empirical class-0 probability vs input covariance between X_1 and X_2 . Here m was 0.1 and the y -intercept was 1.02. 1000 samples were generated for each covariance in the range -2 to 2. The variance of X_1 was 11 and X_2 was 12. There were 10 iterations per covariance.

Figure 5: Class-0 classification probability vs input covariance between X_1 and X_2 . The variances and means are such that the dynamic range of the covariance for valid results is as shown.

4.11.4 Testing Phase

The purpose of the testing phase is to use some of the unused data points and see if they are classified correctly by the trained perceptron. By trained perceptron we mean the perceptron whose weights are set to the last iteration of training

weights. To produce an analytical result for the testing phase, we need the distribution of the testing data and the exact final weights. The variables J_i of Equation (3) are in the testing phase simply scaled versions of the testing data since the weights are now constants. So we have,

$$J_i = w_i^{final} X_i. \quad (26)$$

There is no weight update equation since the weights are finalized. A modified version of Equation (4) becomes the pdf for the new J_i of Equation (26). Once again, we can restrict ourselves first to the $M = 2$ case and find out the pdf of the post-summation variable J . This is put through the hard-limiter to get the final output Y . This variable Y would provide the probabilities of C0 and C1 classification, which can then be stated as the ‘performance’ of the trained perceptron algorithm.

4.12 Other Perceptrons

In this section we consider a few novel perceptron algorithms - the ephaptic perceptron and the branched perceptron.

4.12.1 Ephaptic Perceptron

This perceptron, introduced first in [30], offers joint processing of input data using two neurons that ‘talk’ to one another. It mimics the situation in the nervous system where axons can talk to one another.

New Methodology In this section, we present the results from a modified methodology of viewing, for alpha ranging from 0 through 3, figures 6 through 9. In the new method, we add noise of pre-specified variance to the bias term on the second neuron. To be specific we use the following specifications:

- `b1 = zeros(1,n);`
- `b1(1,1) = b11;`
- `b2 = zeros(1,n);`
- `b2(1,1) = b22 + mynoisevar*randn(1);`
- `lambda1 = -0.1;`
- `lambda2 = -0.5;`

The above represents a ‘differential coupled perceptron set’ [31] where the lambdas can be negative. We used the following settings:

- `noisevar = 0:0.01:0.5;`
- `numiters = 20;%per noisevar`

Delay Compensation Consider two ephaptic perceptrons, A and B, used in parallel. If we ignore the activation step, the two perceptrons can be thought of as a regular stack of two perceptrons’ inputs followed by a two-input, two-output MIMO channel. Suppose there is a T second time lag between the inputs to A and B, but they are required to be simultaneously processed. To achieve this

Figure 6: Mean x -value is 44.7712 and mean y -value is 52.3529.

Figure 7: Mean x -value is 51.9281 and mean y -value is 61.1111.

Figure 8: Mean x -value is 51.0131 and mean y -value is 57.5817.

Figure 9: Mean x -value is 51.2418 and mean y -value is 59.9673.

Figure 10: Axon Branching. Adapted from Figure 2 of [32]. Permission pending.

one only need modify the weights of the MIMO matrix and the delay can be compensated. This will ensure a synchronous processing.

General Observations We find that quadratic coupling in Perceptron 1 yields a statistically significant improvement in performance over no-coupling, linear and cubic coupling. If this is replicable with greater size of the dataset, it could be a promising new way to use a perceptron. The computational processing of even this truncated MNIST data (only 100 training and 25 testing points) took a total of 12 hours on a Windows i9 laptop. The full data set contains 60000 training and 10000 testing points. The impact of data (image) pre-processing on the results might also be important to investigate.

Modifications to Investigate in Future Work Using distinct weight starting points instead of common weights for the two perceptrons, using distinct data vectors for the two perceptrons, and inserting a bona-fide axon after the signum output are some of the modifications that we will investigate in future work. The signum output can also be re-scaled appropriately into a current injection, and likewise for the second neuron.

Analysis of Ephaptic Perceptron In Section 4.11 the regular perceptron was analysed in detail and an analysis for the ephaptic perceptron before and during testing can be carried out along the same lines.

4.12.2 Branched Perceptron

The branched perceptron can be seen as a special case of the ephaptic perceptron with two inputs. One of the input vectors is tied to "1".

In a real neuron, sometimes there are several terminal boutons of a single axon (Figure 10). This branching allows the single neuron to feed its result to several destinations. It is plausible that due to some signal processing at the branching points, the signals going down the various axon branches are not all identical; there may certainly be varying time delays that they carry. But it is certainly necessary to consider all the boutons to determine the overall output of the neuron.

Inspired by this, consider a perceptron where the pointwise product is replaced by a convolution. A convolution can be thought of as producing many pointwise products, just one of which is the “full overlap” pointwise product of the regular perceptron. These additional partial products are summed separately and signumed also separately, thereby representing the signals that reach distinct terminal boutons.

It would be interesting to explore the performance of the branched perceptron in addition to the coupled perceptron and the regular perceptron. This perceptron might be useful when ‘all bits (input data) are not created equal’ [33]. It is distinct from a CNN where convolutional filtering is applied to the input data for feature identification, since here we don’t sum up the convolutional output prior to the activation step. Instead we develop several output branches, effectively creating several slightly different neurons out of one.

4.12.3 Applications: UEP and Slicing

Consider the Unequal Error Protection problem in greater detail [33]. In this setting, if n bits are to be transmitted, a few of them say $n_1 < n$ will be transmitted in such a way that the error probability in decoding them will decay faster than for the rest of the bits. There are thus a larger number of channel output sequences, all of which decode to the special message, as compared to for the ordinary codewords.

Suppose 10 concatenated codewords are provided to the branched perceptron. Suppose further that one of them is special, obviously all are corrupted by noise. By not studying the classification performed by every branch, and focusing only on the central branch output, we are ignoring the possibility that the special codeword could be located in any position. But by considering branching, we ensure that one of the branches (essentially weight permutations) has a high probability of classifying this data vector as containing a special message. In every iteration (longitudinal) all branches are computed in parallel. This would make more sense if all the words corresponding to the special message have a special structure - for example, if they are all obtained by flipping upto k bits, thereby retaining a hamming radius of k .

In the context of 5G slicing, since some network slices may be provided different/higher security than other slices, one may want to use a branched perceptron in analysing the data carried by the network. This would allow highly secure data to be accurately classified as rogue/non-rogue in a quicker convergence time, as compared to less secure slice data. In future work, one could also consider a coupled-branched perceptron, in which both the features of multiple lateral couplings and multiple longitudinal branches are integrated.

5 Simulation of the Solution

In this section we present simulation results showing the performance of the presented Network Random Refresh strategy. Figure 11 shows the performance

Figure 11: Variation of performance with size of the network. For small networks of size less than 20 nodes, the performance with NRR is modestly better than without NRR on average. The gains diminish with larger network sizes and the strategy becomes ineffective as implemented. This is possibly because a small network offers only a handful of routes to the victim whereas larger networks offer a host of possibilities.

of the refresh strategy at a modest refresh probability of 0.15.

Figure 12 shows the performance of the refresh strategy for different refresh probabilities for a modest network size of 20 nodes, averaged over 100 simulation runs.

6 Discussion, Limitations and Conclusion

In this paper, we developed a strategy of network random refresh (NRR) to mitigate the impact of a rogue. We found that the strategy works well consistently for low network sizes less than 20 nodes. For larger networks, the strategy becomes ineffective and works only sporadically. We also proposed a new perceptron algorithm that can be useful in learning about the presence of a rogue in the network. Our NRR strategy is not without its limitations. When one is refreshing the network topology frequently, many benign processes and services could also get disrupted. Processes that need not be secured and can be open also can get unnecessarily disrupted. In future work a more detailed and robust strategy will thus have to be evolved.

In the context of the impact of technology on society [34], networks play

Figure 12: Variation of performance with refresh probability.

an important role. Scalable and secure networks that can be easily deployed in diverse environmental conditions are a boon. Consider, for example, a disaster area 100 sq-kilometer wide, where there is much flooding due to a dam-burst. Villages have been submerged but some survivors exist, having improvised boats and rafts, some on roof-tops of *pucca* houses. In such a setting, when first responders come, they need to be able to rapidly deploy a basic communication infrastructure which is secure. Since crooks are always present to take advantage of others even in a disaster, this security must be of the highest order. 5G rapidly deployable user equipment (UEs) can be distributed to the survivors in order to facilitate communication among themselves and with the relief providers. Later on, post-disaster, the network can be disbanded. This use case has many more technological details that need to be worked out before it can become practicable to execute on the field. Our present work represents only a small step in this direction.

The insights obtained here are relevant in many respects to cortical communication networks. It has been observed by MacNaughton et. al. [35] that packet communication takes place in the cortex as well. At some level, there might also be an ‘application layer’ in the cortex, though this is only a hypothesis at this stage. It would be interesting to investigate whether concepts such as network slicing mimic what happens in biology or not. It is also relevant to point out that deep sleep might be an analog of the NRR strategy proposed herein. However, the poor scaling of NRR performance with network size is a contra-indication of the actual implementation of NRR in brain networks which are quite humongous in size. These overlaps and cross-insights are quite inter-

esting to explore in future work, wherein we will focus on a modified version of this strategy that scales well with network size. We will also need to investigate and develop a strategy for the case when the number of rogues can be large.

As a concluding remark, consciousness in particular and biology in general generate systems which mimic in many ways the very generative structure itself. It also motivates us to ask if the man-made world is not just an extension of the brain(s) that developed it. If this is the case, then fundamental principles govern it, operating in a hierarchical or nested manner. These are ultimately the principles of biophysics. Simple laws such as charge conservation, which govern brain-wide phenomena such as ephaptic coupling or synchronization [36] may therefore ramify at every scale, including the meso- and macro-scale. And these are the laws of the universe since the Big Bang. Thus we see how, in the spirit of David Bohm [37, 38] and the Vedic *rsis*, wholeness is implicit in every part of the subjects which science studies, which are aspects of Nature in general.

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Appendix: Generalization to Three Dimensions

In this appendix, the authors propose to generalize the backpropagation learning rule given in Bechtel and Abrahamsen [39] to higher dimensions. This effort is hoped to mesh well with tortuous models of axon tracts in three dimensions [40] and therefore to provide better learning performance for situations which are inherently three dimensional such as spatial learning.

Next, we provide a few initial guidelines on how to create a three dimensional version of the backpropagation learning rule of Bechtel and Abrahamsen. We begin by defining a new 'del' operator:

$$\nabla_{a_i} = \hat{x} \frac{\partial}{\partial a_{ix}} + \hat{y} \frac{\partial}{\partial a_{iy}} + \hat{z} \frac{\partial}{\partial a_{iz}} \quad (27)$$

where $a_i \vec{=} a_{ix}\hat{x} + a_{iy}\hat{y} + a_{iz}\hat{z}$. We apply this new 'del' operator to the error, defined as

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \left\| (\vec{d}_i - \vec{a}_i) \right\|^2. \quad (28)$$

This yields, immediately, that,

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial a_{ix}} = \sum_i (a_{ix} - d_{ix}), \quad (29)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial a_{iy}} = \sum_i (a_{iy} - d_{iy}), \quad (30)$$

and finally,

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial a_{iz}} = \sum_i (a_{iz} - d_{iz}). \quad (31)$$

All the steps in the derivation can hereafter be done in terms of similar “del” operators. For example, consider another “del” defined thus,

$$\nabla_{netinput_i} = \hat{x} \frac{\partial}{\partial netinput_{ix}} + \hat{y} \frac{\partial}{\partial netinput_{iy}} + \hat{z} \frac{\partial}{\partial netinput_{iz}} \quad (32)$$

If we consider,

$$\|\vec{a}_i\| = \sqrt{a_{ix}^2 + a_{iy}^2 + a_{iz}^2} \quad (33)$$

then,

$$\nabla_{netinput_i} (\|\vec{a}_i\|) = \hat{x} \frac{\partial (\|\vec{a}_i\|)}{\partial netinput_{ix}} + \hat{y} \frac{\partial (\|\vec{a}_i\|)}{\partial netinput_{iy}} + \hat{z} \frac{\partial (\|\vec{a}_i\|)}{\partial netinput_{iz}} \quad (34)$$

with

$$\frac{\partial (\|\vec{a}_i\|)}{\partial netinput_{ix}} = \frac{a_{ix}^2 (1 - a_{ix})}{\sqrt{a_{ix}^2 + a_{iy}^2 + a_{iz}^2}} \quad (35)$$

An important direction of future work is to consider in more detail three dimensional perceptrons where they are precisely inclined and maintain precise separations, besides being branched and coupled. Such geometrical considerations for axon tracts were invoked in [41]. In [42] it was also shown that a tract might be a learning machine and that work can be connected to the present paper. Finally, tortuous coupled perceptrons [43] would perhaps mimic exactly the learning behavior of the real central nervous system.

References

- [1] Zhenyu Liu, Andrea Conti, Sanjoy K Mitter, and Moe Z Win. Communication-efficient distributed learning over networks—part i: Sufficient conditions for accuracy. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 41(4):1081–1101, 2023.
- [2] Anutusha Dogra, Rakesh Kumar Jha, and Shubha Jain. A survey on beyond 5g network with the advent of 6g: Architecture and emerging technologies. *IEEE access*, 9:67512–67547, 2020.

- [3] Aaron French, Jung P Shim, Marten Risius, Kai R Larsen, and Hemant Jain. The 4th industrial revolution powered by the integration of ai, blockchain, and 5g. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 49(1):6, 2021.
- [4] Haijun Zhang, Na Liu, Xiaoli Chu, Keping Long, Abdol-Hamid Aghvami, and Victor CM Leung. Network slicing based 5g and future mobile networks: Mobility, resource management, and challenges. *IEEE communications magazine*, 55(8):138–145, 2017.
- [5] Xenofon Foukas, Georgios Patounas, Ahmed Elmokashfi, and Mahesh K Marina. Network slicing in 5g: Survey and challenges. *IEEE communications magazine*, 55(5):94–100, 2017.
- [6] Godfrey Anuga Akpakwu, Bruno J Silva, Gerhard P Hancke, and Adnan M Abu-Mahfouz. A survey on 5g networks for the internet of things: Communication technologies and challenges. *IEEE access*, 6:3619–3647, 2017.
- [7] Xingqin Lin, Jingya Li, Robert Baldemair, Jung-Fu Thomas Cheng, Stefan Parkvall, Daniel Chen Larsson, Havish Koorapaty, Mattias Frenne, Sorour Falahati, Asbjorn Grovlen, et al. 5g new radio: Unveiling the essentials of the next generation wireless access technology. *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, 3(3):30–37, 2019.
- [8] Syed Rafiul Hussain, Mitziu Echeverria, Omar Chowdhury, Ninghui Li, and Elisa Bertino. Privacy attacks to the 4g and 5g cellular paging protocols using side channel information. *Network and distributed systems security (NDSS) symposium2019*, 2019.
- [9] Rabia Khan, Pardeep Kumar, Dushantha Nalin K Jayakody, and Madhusanka Liyanage. A survey on security and privacy of 5g technologies: Potential solutions, recent advancements, and future directions. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 22(1):196–248, 2019.
- [10] Raja Ettiane, Abdelaali Chaoub, and Rachid Elkouch. Toward securing the control plane of 5g mobile networks against dos threats: Attack scenarios and promising solutions. *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, 61:102943, 2021.
- [11] John A Khan and Md Minhaz Chowdhury. Security analysis of 5g network. In *2021 IEEE International Conference on Electro Information Technology (EIT)*, pages 001–006. IEEE, 2021.
- [12] Tim Bass. Intrusion detection systems and multisensor data fusion. *Communications of the ACM*, 43(4):99–105, 2000.
- [13] Min Seok Lee, Seok Woo Yang, and Sung Won Han. Gaia: Graphical information gain based attention network for weakly supervised point cloud semantic segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, pages 582–591, 2023.

- [14] Katherine H Shutta, Deborah Weighill, Rebekka Burkholz, Marouen Ben Guebila, Dawn L DeMeo, Helena U Zacharias, John Quackenbush, and Michael Altenbuchinger. DRAGON: Determining Regulatory Associations using Graphical models on multi-Omic Networks. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 51(3):e15–e15, 12 2022.
- [15] Di Cao, Junbo Zhao, Jiayang Hu, Yansong Pei, Qi Huang, Zhe Chen, and Weihao Hu. Physics-informed graphical representation-enabled deep reinforcement learning for robust distribution system voltage control. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 2023.
- [16] Renato E Mirollo and Steven H Strogatz. Synchronization of pulse-coupled biological oscillators. *SIAM Journal on Applied Mathematics*, 50(6):1645–1662, 1990.
- [17] John Bonner Buck. Synchronous rhythmic flashing of fireflies. *The Quarterly Review of Biology*, 13(3):301–314, 1938.
- [18] Peter Parham. *The immune system*. Garland Science, 2014.
- [19] Vishwa Teja Alaparthi and Salvatore Domenic Morgera. A multi-level intrusion detection system for wireless sensor networks based on immune theory. *IEEE Access*, 6:47364–47373, 2018.
- [20] Silvia Curteanu and Hugh Cartwright. Neural networks applied in chemistry. i. determination of the optimal topology of multilayer perceptron neural networks. *Journal of Chemometrics*, 25(10):527–549, 2011.
- [21] Ondřej Zelený and Tomas Fryza. Multi-branch multi layer perceptron: A solution for precise regression using machine learning. In *2023 33rd International Conference Radioelektronika (RADIOELEKTRONIKA)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2023.
- [22] Frank Rosenblatt. The perceptron: a probabilistic model for information storage and organization in the brain. *Psychological review*, 65(6):386, 1958.
- [23] Terrence L. Fine. *Feedforward neural network methodology*. Springer, New York, 1999.
- [24] Hans-Dieter Block. The perceptron: A model for brain functioning. i. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 34(1):123, 1962.
- [25] Matt W Gardner and SR Dorling. Artificial neural networks (the multilayer perceptron)—a review of applications in the atmospheric sciences. *Atmospheric environment*, 32(14-15):2627–2636, 1998.
- [26] Bernard Widrow and Michael A Lehr. 30 years of adaptive neural networks: perceptron, madaline, and backpropagation. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 78(9):1415–1442, 1990.

- [27] JK Anlauf and M Biehl. The adatron: an adaptive perceptron algorithm. *Europhysics Letters*, 10(7):687, 1989.
- [28] Hirotugu Akaike. A new look at the statistical model identification. *IEEE transactions on automatic control*, 19(6):716–723, 1974.
- [29] Athanasios Papoulis and S Unnikrishna Pillai. *Probability, random variables and stochastic processes*. 2002.
- [30] Aman Chawla. A mathematical model for the vector ephaptic perceptron. *Zenodo*, 2022.
- [31] Aman Chawla and Salvatore Domenic Morgera. Differential ephaptic networks. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 10(10):2876–2882, 2022.
- [32] Katherine Kalil and Erik W Dent. Branch management: mechanisms of axon branching in the developing vertebrate cns. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 15(1):7–18, 2014.
- [33] Shashi Borade, Barış Nakiboğlu, and Lizhong Zheng. Some fundamental limits of unequal error protection. In *2008 IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory*, pages 2222–2226. IEEE, 2008.
- [34] Aaditeshwar Seth. *Technology and (dis) empowerment: A Call to Technologists*. Emerald Group Publishing, 2022.
- [35] Artur Luczak, Bruce L McNaughton, and Kenneth D Harris. Packet-based communication in the cortex. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 16(12):745–755, 2015.
- [36] Aman Chawla and Salvatore D Morgera. Ephaptic synchronization as a mechanism for selective amplification of stimuli. *BMC Neuroscience*, 15(1):1–1, 2014.
- [37] David Bohm. *Wholeness and the implicate order*. Routledge, 2005.
- [38] David Bohm and Henry P Stapp. *The undivided universe: An ontological interpretation of quantum theory*, 1994.
- [39] William Bechtel and Adele Abrahamsen. *Connectionism and the mind: Parallel processing, dynamics, and evolution in networks*. Blackwell Publishing, 2002.
- [40] Aman Chawla and Salvatore Domenic Morgera. On the geometry of interacting axon tracts in relation to their functional properties. *Commun. Math. Biol. Neurosci.*, 2024:Article–ID, 2024.
- [41] Aman Chawla, Salvatore Morgera, and Arthur Snider. On axon interaction and its role in neurological networks. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics*, 2019.

- [42] Aman Chawla. *On Axon-Axon Interaction via Currents and Fields*. PhD thesis, University of South Florida, 2017.
- [43] Aman Chawla and Salvatore Domenic Morgera. On the geometry of interacting axon tracts in relation to their functional properties. *bioRxiv*, 2022.